

ESTABLISHING THE DOMINANT POSITION OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN THE INTERNAL MARKET OF THE EU

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The topic is current because digital platform operators are quickly taking over the European single digital market, and several players, including the European Commission and European National Competition and Consumer Authorities (like Finland), have voiced concerns about consumer safety and competition in the single digital market. Compared to more traditional business models, digital online platforms may grow rapidly and adapt to changing environments more quickly since they are more dynamic than traditional firms. The market for online platforms is a continuously changing industry. One million EU companies currently sell goods and services online, and over half of small and medium-sized businesses that sell through online marketplaces do so internationally, according to data from the European Commission. At a growth rate of around 14%, the European business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce turnover was predicted to reach approximately €602 billion in 2017.

The European Commission's report states that the EU's official policy for the digital single market legislation is to defend consumer interests and guarantee fair competition in the market.

Since creating a digital single market was one of the goals of the Juncker Commission, the European Union is now working on a number of legislative initiatives aimed at the digital platform economy. In order to protect the four fundamental freedoms of the European Union—the free movement of capital, goods, people, and services as well as the use and access to these digital online platform services under fair competition, the Digital Single Market initiative aims to expand the application of Article 26(2) TFEU to the internet.

Political action is required to encourage the growth of the digital platform economy, and as a result, European enterprises currently incur high expenses to comply with regulations, which is detrimental to the EU's attempts to achieve its economic goals. The method used in this thesis is to examine the laws now in effect inside the European Union and its Economic Zone, as well as how the Commission handles defining a dominant position for digital online platforms that function within the internal market.

Digital platforms are complicated organizations that can function concurrently in several markets that are intricately intertwined. As a result, defining the relevant market and the abuse of dominance in that particular market can be a crucial task for any legislation, giving EU competition law provisions more weight. The focus of the thesis is on European Union law, European competition law, and policies. It also discusses the current meanings of these terms and offers suggestions for potential legislative amendments.

To put it plainly, many of the provisions are too ambiguous, which can result in significant penalties for big companies like Apple, Google, Amazon, and Intel that are not based in the European Union. As a result, the modern definition of dominant market position needs to evolve under competition law regulation since the companies currently operating in the market lack precise means and instructions how to avoid breaking competition rules.

The thesis anticipated conclusion is that there is insufficient clarity in the legislative framework pertaining to the concept of the dominating position for digital online platforms. In addition to discussing the problems arising from the absence of a legal framework and how it impacts practice, the evaluation will concentrate on whether or not this statement is supported. The most optimal solution would be to discover that the case law has supplied complete advice on the topic.

Digital Online Platform

Since the idea of a digital two-sided platform, sometimes known as a multi-sided platform, is still developing, I believe it is important to investigate whether a platform should be considered a separate legal concept and, if so, what that notion should represent. As a general rule, a digital platform should only establish its own concept if it is able to recognize several legal organizations that have similar characteristics and, as a result, need to be reviewed differently than traditional businesses. It is evident from examining the many definitions that platforms must function in a multifaceted market in order to qualify as “platforms”.

In contrast to typical parallel markets, where a corporation has a single vertical interaction with a group of customers, a platform operating in such a market has at least two different client groups (market parties) with which the platform has a horizontal relationship.

A business is a digital online platform, according to Kalimo & Majcher, if it generates indirect network effects among its many clientele. When one consumer group's demand is reliant on another's demand, this is known as an

indirect network effect. For instance, the more vendors (producers) there are, the more consumers (users) marketplace platforms draw. Direct network effects, on the other hand, happen on the same side of the market and include a correlation between the size of one client group and the number of other customers on that side.⁴¹ If there are more customers, network effects are good; if there are fewer users, network effects are negative.

There is disagreement in the literature, nonetheless, over whether the definition of a digital platform necessitates multidirectional indirect network effects or if parallel indirect network effects suffice. It has also been suggested that a platform-neutral pricing structure is necessary for a definition of a digital online platform. When a platform establishes prices that are charged by various market participants at varying levels, this is known as an unneutral pricing system.

The goal of the unneutral pricing structure is to convert indirect network effects into operating profit as much as possible. Some or all of the costs of another client group (money side) will be borne by the group of customers whose demand is the most inelastic, that is, whose demand is not greatly impacted by little price changes. In turn, the other market receives services at prices lower than the marginal cost, either for free or at extremely cheap costs (subsidy side). The definitions in the third and, in my opinion, most pertinent major group state that the digital internet platform serves as a middleman between two or more client groups. For instance, Apple manufactures its own computers on the market, but Microsoft defers to independent manufacturers. Because of this, Microsoft works in a three-way market for end users, software suppliers, and hardware makers, while Apple operates in a two-way market between end users and software providers.

The intermediary platform's purpose is restricted to facilitating direct communication between customer groups; it has no legal or commercial stake in the legal relationships between customer groups. Important aspects of the two-way client interaction, such price and contractual conditions, are not under the intermediate platform's control. According to the definition of a digital online platform, it must have a minimum of two consumer groups that connect with the platform for various reasons.

Since it establishes the degree to which customer demand is interdependent and convergent, a thorough analysis of the various platforms' goals to unite the parties is required. This in turn establishes whether it is necessary to specify one relevant market or several cases. Platforms are frequently separated into

transactional platforms and non-transactional platforms in the economic literature. A transaction platform is a digital network platform designed to connect various market players for an instantaneous and visible transaction.

The objective and comprehension of the transaction platform substitutes are similar across various client groups. For instance, users of one payment card platform might switch to another, and users of another marketplace platform might switch to another. A platform cannot do business without the cooperation of every single consumer group due to the multidirectional positive indirect network effects generated by transactional platforms. As a result, transaction platforms cannot leave some markets without leaving others, in contrast to conventional vertically integrated businesses that operate in parallel marketplaces.

Social media and content platforms are examples of non-transactional platforms that serve as middlemen between various market actors to facilitate non-transactional interactions. Market players' opinions about which services take the place of the platform's services vary, as do the motivations of various platform customer groups to engage with the platform ecosystem. Since beneficial network effects are only produced in one direction, non-transactional platforms can likewise function without the assistance of an additional consumer base. The platform can continue to function as a traditional business rather than a digital internet platform if it divests from another customer group. Another similar, but less widely used breakdown is based on the platform's position as either a party integrator or an audience provider. The features of so called matching platform are similar to those of transaction platforms, but the concept of matching platform is broader, including transactional platforms, with the purpose of enables other direct and visible interaction between different market participants. The concept of an audience providing platform (advertising platform) is similar to that of non-audience providers definition of transaction platforms, and the purpose of such platform is to enable one attracting the attention of another customer group.

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